

Project number: 874662

Project Acronym: HEAP

Project Title: Human Exposome Assessment Platform

Project Website URL: <https://heap-exposome.eu/>

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Work Package 7

Data interoperability and data sharing

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Project Deliverable

D7.4: Assessment of Interoperability and Data Quality

Deliverable due date: 2025-05-31

Deliverable due month: 64

Document history

Version	Date	Changes	By	Reviewed
1.0	2025-06-15	First draft	Bettina Monschein, Emilian Jungwirth, Heimo Müller	
1.1	2025-06-27	Input by project partners	Frederik Trier Møller, Ville Pimenoff	Frederik Trier Møller, Ville Pimenoff, Roxana Merino
2.0	2025-06-30	Final version	Project partners	Roxana Merino Joakim Dillner

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of the FAIR maturity and interoperability assessment conducted across selected cohorts within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP). The objective was to evaluate the current status of data interoperability and FAIRness—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—across six representative cohorts, using a harmonised set of indicators adapted from the Research Data Alliance (RDA) FAIR Data Maturity Model.

Each cohort has been assessed through a combination of metadata inspection, stakeholder interviews, and spider graph visualisations to compare baseline (pre-HEAP) and post-intervention states. The cohorts encompass diverse data types, ranging from registry-based datasets (e.g., Finnish Maternity and Vaccination Cohorts) to novel digital health data (e.g., Wearable Cohort and My Purchases Cohort), as well as highly curated research cohorts, such as the Tirol Gesund Lifestyle Atlas.

Key findings indicate that all cohorts have improved their FAIR maturity across most categories, particularly in the Findable and Accessible dimensions, where enhancements have been made to persistent identifiers, licensing metadata, and machine-access protocols. Interoperability remains challenging in cases where cohorts are structurally standalone or still in the feasibility phase—e.g., the Wearable Cohort lacks references to external metadata. In the Reusable dimension, cohorts such as My Purchases are constrained by the lack of established community standards, which limits full alignment despite improvements in licensing and provenance.

The analysis confirms that targeted interventions, including the use of the BIBBOX toolbox, have improved metadata quality and FAIRness even in settings with limited initial infrastructure. For emerging data domains, indicators marked "not applicable" are contextually interpreted rather than penalised.

This assessment provides actionable insights for HEAP sustainability, contributes to the FAIR-by-design strategy, and lays the groundwork for cohort onboarding protocols. Future work will focus on integrating semantic linkages, aligning with GA4GH interoperability profiles, and supporting continuous improvement through feedback loops with data providers and end users.

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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interfaces
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
BIBBOX	Basic Infrastructure Building Box
CON	Consumer Cohort
COVID-19	coronavirus disease 2019
CSC	IT Center for Science, Finland
CSC	Cervical Screening Cohort
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EHEN	THE EUROPEAN HUMAN EXPOSOME NETWORK
ELIXIR	European Life Sciences Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FDP	FAIR data point
FICAN-MID	Cancer Center of Inner Finland
FMC	Finish Maternity Cohort
HEAP	HUMAN EXPOSOME ASSESSMENT PLATFORM
HPV	Human Papillomavirus
HPV	HPV vaccination cohort

KI	Karolinska Institutet
LSC	TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas
MAT	Maternity Cohort
MIABIS	Minimum Information About Blobank Data Sharing
Molgenis	Molgenis is a collaborative open-source project on a mission to generate excellent software infrastructure for life science research.
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry
PID	Persistent Identifier
PI	Principal Investigator
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SAS	Self Assessment Service
STD	Sexually transmitted disease
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
UIBK	University of Innsbruck, Austria
UOULU	University of Oulu, Finland
WDC	Wearable Data Collection Study

1 Introduction

The HEAP project (Human Exposome Assessment Platform) aims to enable high-quality, cross-disciplinary research into the effects of environmental exposures on human health. To do so, HEAP integrates data from diverse sources—such as population cohorts, registries, and wearable devices—into a common infrastructure designed to facilitate long-term reuse and interoperability. Ensuring that such data are **FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**—is a foundational principle of the project and essential for maximising scientific and societal value.

The **FAIR Data Principles**, first formulated in 2016, have become a cornerstone of responsible data stewardship. They are not only technical guidelines, but also cultural drivers for data sharing, enabling machine-actionable metadata, transparent licensing, and integration across institutional and national boundaries. For HEAP, applying the FAIR principles ensures that the diverse datasets entering the platform can be efficiently located, understood, accessed, reused, and linked by both humans and computational agents.

This deliverable presents the results of a structured **FAIRness assessment** of selected HEAP cohorts. Such an assessment is critical for identifying existing gaps and strengths in metadata quality, access infrastructure, semantic integration, and reuse conditions. It also helps ensure that data entering the HEAP Information Commons meets a level of interoperability required for long-term sustainability and downstream use, including in policy and precision health research.

To support FAIR implementation, HEAP has established a multi-pronged strategy that includes:

- **Training workshops and online tutorials** to introduce FAIR principles and tools to cohort owners and data stewards;
- A set of **guiding materials and videos** tailored to real-world exposome data scenarios;
- The deployment of **BIBBOX**, a modular, FAIR-enabling software toolbox used to host metadata catalogues and cohort-specific services;
- **Continuous support and feedback loops** between the FAIR assessment team and cohort leads;
- And a **two-stage evaluation process**, comprising an initial baseline assessment and a follow-up evaluation after targeted improvements.

Together, these activities have enabled a cohort-specific improvement path while contributing to HEAP's overarching goal of building a FAIR-by-design exposome research ecosystem. This deliverable, documents the methodology and results of the assessment, providing cohort-specific insights to guide future development and FAIR onboarding efforts.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Chapter 2 gives a brief overview of the six HEAP cohorts. In Chapter 3, the HEAP FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service is explained. Chapter 4 describes the results of the evaluation of the FAIR status of each of the six HEAP cohorts. Chapter 5 gives a brief summary, and Chapter 6 provides a list of references referred to in this document. In the Annexe of this document, the complete list of the FAIR indicators used in the HEAP FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service can be found.

2 HEAP Cohorts

The overall goal of HEAP is to enable global collaborative exposome research towards cost-effective health interventions. HEAP provides a system for obtaining, managing, sharing and analysing exposome data. Large-scale, comprehensive, population-based systems have been exploited to build sustainable systems for measuring the human exposome and its impact on health. The HEAP consortium launches innovative scientific analysis methods beyond state-of-the-science technologies, high-throughput epigenomics and metagenomics methods, computation resources, wearable exposome sensors, and applied Artificial Intelligence (HEAP DMP, Müller et al., 2020 – updated 2023).

HEAP has developed a standardised, integrated, and generic informatics platform that enables the creation of collaborative networks for the joint production of consistent and actionable knowledge to tackle the effects of exposome on health and society.

Data are generated in 6 research sub-projects

1. HEAP - Cervical Screening Cohort
2. HEAP - Finnish Maternity Cohort
3. HEAP - HPV Vaccination Cohort
4. HEAP - Consumer Cohort - My Purchases Cohort
5. HEAP - Wearable Data Collection Study
6. HEAP - Lifestyle Cohort - TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas

2.1 HEAP - Cervical Screening Cohort

Leading partner (PI): KI, Joakim Dillner

The main purpose of cervical screening is to screen all women between 23 and 70, to prevent the occurrence of invasive cervical cancer by detecting and removing precancerous lesions, which, if left untreated, could develop into invasive cervical cancer. As a result, the cervical screening program has provided the National Clinical Cytology Biobank samples corresponding to around 670,000 unique women (updated 2024). Data are collected from the samples taken in the organised cervical screening program in the Stockholm region, the capital region of Sweden, and national health registers and quality register databases.

The cervical screening cohort provides samples from healthy tissue, pre-neoplastic lesions and cancer. The sequencing analysis of specimens, together with metadata, aims to identify and characterise risk factors that may impact the risk of having the disease or being healthy. The results will help citizens understand the risk factors that increase the risk of cervical cancer and other diseases.

2.2 HEAP - Finnish Maternity Cohort

Leading partner (PI): UOULU, Ville Pimenoff, Heljä-Marja Surcel; KI/FICAN-MID, Matti Lehtinen.

The HEAP Maternity cohort aims to establish a population-based cohort biobank. The data collected spans calendar time and across generations. Hence, the relation to HEAP elucidates the exposome in this context, considering it over time and across generations.

The baseline cohort data for approximately 1,000,000 healthy participants consists of consented participation data. Registry linkage will be done by the original data provider only, and anonymous data (not pseudo-anonymised) will be delivered. The origin of the data is the Finnish National prenatal screening, with additional FMC screening results (HIV, syphilis, hepatitis B, rubella). CSC will provide data through controlled access after approval of the data owner(s). The results will help citizens understand the risk factors that increase the risk of cancer and other diseases.

2.3 HEAP - HPV Vaccination Cohort

Leading partner (PI): KI/FICAN-MID, Ville Pimenoff and Matti Lehtinen.

The HEAP HPV vaccination cohort aims to establish a randomised stratified intervention cohort. In this context, the exposome refers to the cumulative impact of exposure to health interventions over time.

The baseline data for 60,000 healthy participants consists of the participating cohort data. Registry linkage will be done by the original data provider only, and anonymous data (not pseudo-anonymised) will be delivered.

All data collected come from an intervention trial follow-up, with additional STD follow-up results (cytology, HPV and chlamydia) available. CSC provides data through controlled access after the approval of the data owner(s). A subset of the sample is used to generate microbiome metagenomic data. The expected size for the baseline data is in the gigabyte range, while the sequence data is expected to be in the terabyte range.

The results will help citizens understand the risk factors that increase the risk of cancer and other diseases.

2.4 HEAP - Consumer Cohort - My Purchases Cohort

Leading partner (PI): SSI, Frederik Trier Møller

The HEAP Consumer cohort aims to use consumer purchase data to continuously model and assess the impact of household-consumed exposomes on health. The aim is to identify

purchases that may impact health and provide input to an efficient platform for handling and analysing large amounts of data on environmental exposures and their health effects.

Data are collected from commercial digital receipt providers (such as start-up company Storebox) and, if possible, loyalty programmes of retailers (such as COOP, pending approval). The data are reused from various sources, including Danish registers, quality databases, research projects, digital receipt solutions, and loyalty programs.

The results will help citizens identify and avoid products that increase the risk of one or more diseases.

2.5 HEAP - Wearable Data Collection Study

Leading partner (PI): KI, Michael Snyder; KI/UOULU, Ville Pimenoff.

The HEAP wearable device study aims to establish a proof-of-concept study for monitoring biological and chemical environmental exposures (i.e. exposome) during pregnancy. The environmental data are collected during HEAP with a research plan approved by the Scientific Ethics Committee at the University of Oulu (Finland, PI: Ville Pimenoff). The project aims to demonstrate if biological and chemical exposomes can be monitored during pregnancy with personalised longitudinal sampling over several months. The objective is to monitor exposures in pregnant women in relation to healthy childbearing and produce continuous personal exposome profiling of the participants.

All wearable device data are collected for the approved research plan during HEAP to recruit 100 pregnant/non-pregnant women for a pilot investigation on how the exposome may influence pregnancy and human health in general. The pilot follows these 100 women to investigate how the exposome may change and influence the health of the mother in different environments, such as urban or rural surroundings. Participants are asked to carry the device with them for four months to monitor their personal exposures. Samples are collected by the participant at two-week intervals and stored temporarily in a -20 degrees freezer holder before being delivered to the lab. Then, they are stored in a -80 degrees freezer monthly. The samples are collected and sent to the laboratory on a monthly basis.

The pilot study monitors multiple exposures and health measurements from wearable sensors that collect airborne biological and chemical particulate matter, as well as toxic substances such as toxins, viruses, bacteria, fungal spores, animal debris, and plant pollen. This solution will provide progress towards personal exposome profiling and agnostic identification of environmental risk factors.

CSC provides the non-sensitive part of the dataset through controlled access after the approval of the data owners and the data access committee.

2.6 HEAP - Lifestyle Cohort - TirolGESUND Lifestyle Atlas

The main aim of the HEAP Lifestyle cohort within the TirolGESUND study (NCT05678426) is to investigate dynamics in DNA methylation risk signatures associated with ageing and women's cancers in the presence of non-pharmacological disease-preventing interventions.

Specifically, the effects of two lifestyle changes —smoking cessation or interval fasting with or without ketogenic dietary supplementation, in addition to guided, targeted exercise —have been evaluated over a 6-month intervention period. Several biological samples that may act as surrogate samples for tissues at risk of (age-related) disease are collected at baseline and every two months for 6 months. Optionally, biological samples have been collected at 12 and 18 months after initiation of the intervention. The results of the study in the TirolGESUND Lifestyle atlas will inform future preventive intervention studies.

All data originate from measurements derived from biological specimens collected, clinical observations made, or fitness tracker devices worn by participants within the TirolGESUND study. Following the initial publication of the study data, the DNA methylation data and other clinical data are deposited in a secure, controlled-access repository (European Genome-Phenome Archive).

The cohort comprises methylation and other omic data from > 3,000 samples from 156 women (>3 samples per visit, 4 visits).

The results from this study will help citizens understand the factors that decrease the risk of cancer or other age-related diseases, that individual factors play a key role in cancer development, and that individual risk prediction may be an option supporting cancer prevention in the future.

3 FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service (SAS)

As part of task 7.3 to evaluate the interoperability and FAIRness of the cohorts' data sets, which have been assessed and reviewed as described in Chapter 4 of this deliverable D7.4, we have developed a software tool, the FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service. Due to the pandemic and several related delays, the establishment of the FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service has been delayed.

The guided Self-Assessment helps and assists HEAP researchers to understand whether their data and metadata are FAIR. According to the FAIR Data Maturity Model (FAIR Data Model Working Group, 2020), the FAIR principles are defined as “inspiring concepts... that enable both machines and humans to find, access, interoperate and re-use data and metadata”. The FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service shall assess (first guided, then independently) the quality of how data is stored. The FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service can be accessed, worked with and reused by the same or other researchers in the future. The survey of the FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service is accessible online through the following link: <https://heap.bibbox.org/surveys/?s=XC8YLX8W8R>

FAIR Data SAS Concept

The FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service (SAS) helps to evaluate whether data meet the criteria of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The SAS is based on the FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines. This FAIR data model framework consists of indicators, priorities and evaluation methods.

Indicators

Indicators are derived from the FAIR principles and represent measurable aspects of each principle. We have adopted the indicators developed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (2020). In the Figure below, examples of indicators are listed regarding the principles of Findability and Accessibility.

The complete list of indicators used in the HEAP FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service is included in the Annex of this document.

FAIR	ID	Indicator	Priority
F1	RDA-F1-01M	Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier	●●● Essential
F1	RDA-F1-01D	Data is identified by a persistent identifier	●●● Essential
F1	RDA-F1-02M	Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	●●● Essential
F1	RDA-F1-02D	Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	●●● Essential
F2	RDA-F2-01M	Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	●●● Essential
F3	RDA-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier for the data	●●● Essential
F4	RDA-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-01M	Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	●● Important
A1	RDA-A1-02M	Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-02D	Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-03M	Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-03D	Data identifier resolves to a digital object	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-04M	Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-04D	Data is accessible through standardised protocol	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-05D	Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)	●● Important
A1.1	RDA-A1.1-01M	Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	●●● Essential
A1.1	RDA-A1.1-01D	Data is accessible through a free access protocol	●● Important
A1.2	RDA-A1.2-01D	Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	● Useful

Figure 1: Examples of Indicators F (findable) and A (accessible)

Priorities

Each of the indicators has been assigned a priority level: Essential, Important, or Useful.

Definition of the indicator priorities according to the FAIR Data Maturity Model (FAIR Data Maturity Model, 2020):

Essential: Such an indicator addresses an aspect that is of the utmost importance to achieve FAIRness under most circumstances, or, conversely, FAIRness would be practically impossible to achieve if the indicator were not satisfied.

Important: Such an indicator addresses an aspect that might not be of the utmost importance under specific circumstances, but its satisfaction, if at all possible, would substantially increase FAIRness.

Useful: Such an indicator addresses an aspect that is nice-to-have but is not necessarily indispensable.

Evaluation Method

Two different evaluation methods are presented by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group to evaluate and measure the individual indicators: “measuring progress” and “measuring pass-or-fail”. For the FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service, we have opted to use the evaluation method “measuring progress” as it is best suited to answer the question of “How can the FAIRness of this data be improved?”. To measure progress according to the FAIR Data Maturity Model, the maturity level is determined for each indicator. In the FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service, we use five maturity levels:

- 0 - not applicable
- 1 - not being considered yet
- 2 - under consideration or in planning phase
- 3 - in implementation phase
- 4 - fully implemented

For each indicator, the maturity level is determined.

FAIR Data SAS Questionnaire

In the FAIR Data Self-Assessment Service, data are collected via a RedCap questionnaire based on the guidelines described above. Specifically, the maturity level for each indicator is collected.

Questionnaire Design

An iterative approach was used to elaborate the questionnaire for the self-assessment service. Figure 2 shows the initial draft of the questionnaire, and Figure 4 shows the final version.

Figure 2: First version of the RedCap questionnaire

Starting from the first version of the RedCap questionnaire (as shown in Figure 2), the following steps have been taken iteratively in order to facilitate linkage of the questionnaire with the respective data cohort and in order to improve usability of the questionnaire.

Making the questionnaire distinct

The Self-Assessment Service is used to evaluate the FAIRness of a specific data cohort. Initially, the linkage between the questionnaire (and the subsequent report) and the corresponding data cohort has been made by the contact person's email address, which has to be provided in the questionnaire. However, if one person fills out the questionnaire for multiple, different data cohorts, the report can no longer be clearly linked to the data cohorts in question. Thus, in order to solve this problem, more attributes have been introduced in the questionnaire:

- Cohort name
- Cohort ID (required)
- Institution
- Name of the contact person

The introduction of the Cohort ID in the questionnaire allows for a clear linkage. Furthermore, together with the date the questionnaire has been answered, multiple reports can be clearly linked to a data cohort in the correct order, regardless of the contact person.

Facilitate ease of use

To facilitate the questionnaire's usability, we have implemented an introductory text that gives a brief summary of the Self-Assessment-Service's aims.

Furthermore, help texts have been included with each question to support people in filling out the questionnaire correctly. The texts are taken from the FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines, 2020. The help texts have been implemented in the form of tooltips, which are shown when the user hovers the mouse cursor over the information icon (white 'i' on blue round background). An example of such a tooltip can be seen in Figure 3. In this example, the tooltip for question A1-04D is displayed.

Figure 3: Question A1-04D and Tooltip for Question A1-04D

The tooltips were implemented using the REDCap external module “Form Field Tooltip” in version 3.2. The module is part of the REDCap third-party module repository and can also be found on GitHub.

Figure 4: Final Version of the RedCap questionnaire for the HEAP SAS

FAIR Data SAS Report

Our SAS Reporting tool has been created as a Java Service - based on SPARK (Framework for Computer Clustering). The service is triggered when a questionnaire is completed. It collects data from the RedCap questionnaire and automatically generates a report, which is sent to the given contact and, if specified, to the HEAP-Team. The user can specify whether they create the report for themselves for internal use or also like to share the data with the Consortium. The report is generated using TIBCO JasperSoft. To generate the report, we have created a JasperSoft JRXML template. Our service fills the template variables with data collected in RedCap. Based on the data, the appropriate maturity level of the individual indicator is “checked” in the report (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Example of one indicator in the final report. In this example, the maturity level 2 - under consideration or in planning phase - is checked/selected. Furthermore, the indicator ID (F1-01M) and the priority level (Essential) are visible.

To facilitate the easy linkage of a report to the data cohort, a variable filename for the report has been introduced. The report's filename follows the following convention:

“Report - FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service - *date* - *cohort_id*”

- *date* refers to the date the questionnaire was filled out and submitted
- *cohort_id* refers to the Cohort ID provided in the questionnaire

To facilitate the report's usability, we have implemented an introductory text that gives a brief summary of the Self-Assessment-Service's aims. This should be especially helpful in cases where the people working with the report are not the ones who took the questionnaire.

The report's introduction also explains spider graphs and restates the 5 maturity levels of each FAIR indicator (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Five maturity levels

Spider Graph Design

The report generated by the SAS reporting tool includes four spider graphs to give an overview of a data set's current Fairness. Each spider graph represents one of the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability).

A spider graph, spider chart or radar chart is a two-dimensional chart to display multivariate data. The spider graph can display multiple quantitative variables as long as they have the same range (e.g. from 0 to 4). Therefore, it is necessary to assign a numeric value to each maturity level (see Figure 9) in order to display an indicator's maturity level in a spider graph. In the spider graph, each variable is represented by an axis; the relative position and angle of the axes is typically uninformative (Figure 10). Values of adjacent variables (axes) are connected by a line. It is also possible to plot multiple data series, which share the same variables in one spider graph. In this case, each series is represented by a different line.

Figure 7: Schematic spider graph

JasperSoft (i.e. the software used for creation of the SAS report, as described above) allows the generation of spider graphs. However, this can only be done if the data are correctly provided. Data must be aggregated to a matrix and cannot be provided as singular variables of different values. Therefore, the RedCap data needs to be put into a tabular/matrix format with the columns Series, Values and Categories for each FAIR principle. Indicators are in the

category column, and the corresponding numeric maturity level values are in the values column. An internal mapping of indicators to indicatorID is necessary. The spider graph can only display numeric values. Therefore, a conversion of maturity level to numeric values is also necessary. It is also necessary to include the original data in the data tabular/matrix in addition to the aggregated categories and values columns, as the original data is used to fill in the maturity level of each indicator in the report.

We have improved the spider graph design over multiple iterations, aiming to improve readability and interpretability with each iteration. The different spider graph design versions can be seen in Figures 8-11.

Figure 8: Version 1 of the spider graph

Figure 9: Version 2 of the spider graph. Category/Indicator labels have been changed to their ID to improve readability

Figure 10: Version 3 of the spider graph. Margin has been increased to improve readability.

Figure 11: Final Version of the spider graph. Markings for the maturity levels from 0 (not applicable) to 4 (fully implemented) have been added.

Figure 12 depicts the final spider graph design as displayed in the SAS report. It shows the spider graphs for the indicators of the 4 FAIR aspects (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) in a 2x2 grid.

Figure 12: Definite spider graph design for each FAIR principle in a 2 by 2 grid.

Banner Design

We have followed the official guidelines of the project HEAP website regarding the design of the banner and the logo composition for the SAS.

Additionally, the final banner design for the SAS report (as shown in Figure 13) has been implemented in accordance with the HEAP graphic guidelines.

Figure 13: Final banner design for the SAS report

4 Evaluation Results

The FAIR status of each cohort has been assessed through a combination of metadata inspection, stakeholder interviews, and spider graph visualisations to compare baseline (pre-HEAP) and post-intervention states. In the first half of the project, the cohort PIs assessed the status in terms of the FAIRness of their cohorts using the SAS (as explained in Section 3 of this document) themselves. The second assessment of the cohorts achieved its results through the evaluation guidance of WP7 in the last year of the project.

The following subsections describe the results of these evaluations in greater detail for each of the six HEAP cohorts.

4.1 Cervical Cancer Screening Cohort

The Cervical Cancer Screening Cohort is one of the largest and most established data sources within HEAP, built on a long-standing national program involving over 670,000 women. However, **a baseline FAIR self-assessment at the start of the HEAP project could not be completed**. This has been due to the exceptional circumstances during the early phase of the project, when clinical institutions and healthcare partners have been operating under pandemic-related constraints. In particular, hospital resources have focused on the COVID-19 response, and data infrastructure improvements in non-COVID domains have been temporarily deprioritised.

Despite this initial gap, the **current FAIR maturity assessment**—based on the assessment of the cohort conducted in 2024—demonstrates a solid level of maturity across all four FAIR principles, with especially strong performance in **Findability** and **Accessibility**.

Report

FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service

Indicators for Findable

Indicators for Accessible

Indicators for Interoperable

Indicators for Reusable

Although the initial FAIR self-assessment has been delayed, the **Cervical Cancer Screening Cohort has achieved a high degree of FAIR maturity** through structured improvements during the HEAP project. Its strong foundation in data quality, regulatory compliance, and population coverage makes it a cornerstone for future exposome and AI-enabled health research. To further enhance its interoperability, emphasis should now be placed on linking the cohort to external metadata ecosystems and implementing machine-readable community standards.

The cohort has implemented persistent identifiers for both metadata (**F1-01M**) and data (**F1-01D**), and metadata are structured to support harvesting and indexing (**F4-01M**). Unique identifiers (**F1-02M**, **F1-02D**) and inclusion of data references in metadata (**F3-01M**) are in place. Rich metadata (**F2-01M**) is also available, enabling effective dataset discovery through catalogues and repositories.

Most indicators in the Accessibility domain show high maturity. Metadata contains access and licensing information (**A1-01M**), and manual access to both data and metadata is ensured (**A1-02M/D**). Persistent resolvability of identifiers (**A1-03M/D**) is implemented, and metadata remains available even after data access periods lapse (**A2-01M**). While automated machine access (**A1-05D**) and fully standardised protocols (**A1-04M/D**) are still being refined, overall infrastructure supports secure and controlled access via CSC.

Progress in Interoperability is evident but still evolving. Standardised knowledge representations (**I1-01M/D**) and machine-readable vocabularies (**I1-02M/D**, **I2-01M**) are partially implemented. However, indicators that require **references to external metadata and data (e.g., I3-01M/D, I3-02M/D)** are at a low level, reflecting the dataset's historical design as a standalone national registry. Enhancing semantic interoperability will be a key future objective as the cohort becomes further integrated into European data infrastructures.

The Reusability profile of the cohort is relatively mature. Metadata includes relevant attributes for reuse (**R1-01M**), licensing is documented (**R1.1-01M**), and steps toward standard and machine-readable reuse licenses (**R1.1-02M/03M**) have been taken. Provenance information (**R1.2-01M/02M**) is present, and compliance with community standards (**R1.3-01M/D**) is progressing. Some indicators for machine-readable standard compliance (**R1.3-02M/D**) still offer room for improvement, likely due to the legacy data structures and lack of harmonised exposome standards during initial cohort design.

4.2 FMC- Finnish Maternity Cohort

The **Finnish Maternity Cohort** has improved across nearly all indicators, with the most notable enhancements in **Accessibility** and **Reusability**. A few indicators, particularly on the **Findable** and **Interoperable** axes (e.g. F1-02D, I3-02D), have remained unchanged, indicating areas that may still need targeted improvement. In particular, the Finnish Maternity Cohort (FMC) has demonstrated notable improvements across all four dimensions of the FAIR data principles—

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—following targeted enhancement efforts. A comparison of the radar plots, where the blue dashed line represents the baseline and the red filled area the improved state, reveals both broad progress and specific areas where maturity remained unchanged.

Within the **Findable** dimension, most indicators show improvement. The indicators **F1-01M** and **F1-01D**, which assess whether metadata and data are identified by persistent identifiers, have increased in maturity, as has **F1-02M**, which checks for globally unique identifiers in metadata. Furthermore, **F2-01M**, related to the richness of metadata provided to support discoverability, and **F4-01M**, indicating whether metadata can be harvested and indexed, also show clear enhancement. However, the indicators **F3-01M** (metadata includes the identifier for the data) and **F1-02D** (data have a globally unique identifier) have not exhibited any change, suggesting these have already been implemented or still need attention.

The **Accessible** category shows some of the most substantial improvements. Nearly all indicators, including **A1-01M** (metadata contains access information), **A1-02M** and **A1-02D** (manual accessibility of metadata and data), **A1-03M** and **A1-03D** (identifier resolvability), and **A2-01M** (metadata availability after data are no longer available), have demonstrated enhanced compliance. Notably, access via free protocols (**A1.1-01M/D**) and support for authenticated access (**A1.2-02D**) have also improved. A minor or no improvement has been observed for **A1-04M** and **A1-04D** (standardised protocol access), and **A1-05D** (machine-based automatic access), pointing to areas where the technical infrastructure might already be stable or still under development.

Regarding **Interoperability**, the cohort has also progressed in key areas. Both **I1-01M/D**, which assesses the use of standardised knowledge representations, and **I1-02M/D**, focusing on machine-readable formats, have advanced in maturity. The application of FAIR-compliant vocabularies (**I2-01M**) and inclusion of references to other metadata (**I3-01M**) have improved, as are more advanced indicators like **I3-03M** and **I3-04M**, which refer to qualified metadata and data references. Nonetheless, **I3-01D**, **I3-02M**, and **I3-02D** show no change, indicating potential gaps in referencing practices or a lack of structural metadata links on the data level.

In the **Reusable** domain, FMC has made systematic improvements. **R1-01M**, which ensures the presence of sufficient metadata attributes for reuse, shows clear enhancement, as does **R1.1-01M**, related to licensing information. Compliance with standard reuse licenses (**R1.1-02M**) and machine-readable license formats (**R1.1-03M**) has also improved. Provenance documentation—both community-specific (**R1.2-01M**) and cross-community (**R1.2-02M**)—has been strengthened. Indicators tied to community standards compliance (**R1.3-01M/D**) and machine-understandable expression of standards (**R1.3-02M**) have also improved.

However, **R1.3-02D**, which evaluates whether the data (not just metadata) is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard, remains unchanged.

4.3 HPV-Vaccination Cohort

The FAIR maturity of the Vaccination Cohort has improved significantly in Findability, Accessibility, and Reusability. The limitations seen in Interoperability indicators primarily stem from **non-applicability** rather than implementation gaps, due to the dataset’s standalone design without embedded references to external data sources. As such, future efforts might

not aim to improve these areas unless integration into broader data ecosystems becomes necessary.

In particular, the **Vaccination Cohort** exhibits a generally strong improvement in its FAIR data maturity profile across the dimensions of **Findable**, **Accessible**, and **Reusable**, while progress in **Interoperable** indicators is more limited, primarily due to the dataset's inherent characteristics, which do not include structured references to other data or metadata sources.

The radar plot for Findable indicators shows notable improvements in almost all areas. Indicators such as **F1-01M** and **F1-01D** (persistent identifiers for metadata and data), **F1-02M** (globally unique identifier for metadata), and **F4-01M** (harvestable and indexable metadata) have advanced significantly. **F3-01M**, which concerns metadata containing the data identifier, also shows measurable improvement. **F2-01M**, referring to the richness of metadata, demonstrates substantial gains, reflecting more complete and descriptive metadata. **F1-02D** remains unchanged, suggesting that while metadata identifiers have improved, the data itself still lacks globally unique identifiers.

Within the Accessible dimension, the Vaccination Cohort has improved across nearly all indicators. Key gains are visible in **A1-01M** (metadata includes access information), **A1-02M/D** (manual accessibility of metadata and data), and **A2-01M** (metadata availability even after the data becomes inaccessible). Also improved are **A1.1-01M/D** (free access protocols), **A1.2-02D** (authenticated access), and **A1-05D** (automatic accessibility for machines). Improvements in **A1-04M/D** (standardised protocols) and **A1-03M/D** (identifier resolvability) indicate that technical accessibility infrastructure has been strengthened considerably.

The Interoperability indicators present a clear distinction: while improvements are seen in **I1-01M/D** and **I1-02M/D** (standardised and machine-readable knowledge representations), **I2-01M/D** (FAIR-compliant vocabularies) also advanced modestly. However, several indicators—**I3-01M**, **I3-01D**, **I3-02M/D**, **I3-03M**, and **I3-04M**—remain at the lowest level. This can be attributed to the nature of the Vaccination Cohort dataset, which is primarily a stand-alone dataset and does **not** contain embedded or linked references to other datasets or external metadata records. Thus, indicators that rely on cross-referencing (which are essential for full interoperability in federated environments) are simply not applicable in this case. This should not necessarily be viewed as a deficiency, but rather a reflection of appropriate design for a well-bounded use case.

In terms of Reusability, the Vaccination Cohort shows comprehensive improvements. **R1-01M** (metadata include relevant attributes for reuse) and **R1.1-01M** (reuse licensing information) are strong. Similarly, **R1.1-02M** and **R1.1-03M** (reference to standard and machine-readable licenses) show a clear gain. Provenance information, both community-specific (**R1.2-01M**) and

cross-community (**R1.2-02M**), has also been improved. Compliance with community standards (**R1.3-01M/D**) and machine-understandable community formats (**R1.3-02M**) has been enhanced. **R1.3-02D** remains unchanged, possibly due to the lack of standardisation in expressing data-level community standards.

4.4 Lifestyle Cohort-TIROLGesund Lifestyle Atlas

The **TIROLGesund Lifestyle Atlas** cohort has achieved high FAIR maturity across all dimensions. Unlike datasets that are structurally limited in Interoperability, this cohort takes full advantage of linked data principles and integrates cross-references effectively. The results suggest a deliberate and successful effort to align with FAIR data best practices, supporting both technical interoperability and long-term reuse. Minor gaps in machine-based

accessibility remain, but overall, this cohort stands out as a model for mature FAIR implementation.

In particular, the **Lifestyle Cohort – TIROLGesund Lifestyle Atlas** exhibits a well-rounded and comprehensive improvement across all FAIR principles, demonstrating a high level of FAIR data maturity after the implementation of targeted improvements. The radar plots indicate substantial gain compared to the baseline (blue dashed line), especially in **Interoperability** and **Reusability**, while also maintaining a strong upward trend in **Findability** and **Accessibility**.

The Lifestyle Cohort shows consistent improvements across all Findability indicators. Both **F1-01M** and **F1-01D**, which concern persistent identifiers for metadata and data, respectively, reach the highest level of maturity. Globally unique identifiers for metadata (**F1-02M**) and data (**F1-02D**) have also improved. Notably, **F2-01M**, which measures the richness of metadata to support discovery, shows strong enhancement, indicating better descriptive and contextual metadata. **F3-01M** (inclusion of data identifier in metadata) and **F4-01M** (metadata are harvestable/indexable) both have improved as well, demonstrating a well-structured approach to data documentation and exposure.

Significant progress is also evident in the Accessibility dimension. The indicator **A1-01M** (metadata contains information to access the data) reaches the maximum score. Indicators **A1-02M** and **A1-02D**, reflecting manual accessibility of metadata and data, show improved maturity. Enhancements in **A1-03M/D** (identifier resolvability), **A1-04M/D** (standardised protocol access), and **A1.1-01M/D** (free access protocols) demonstrate a robust and interoperable technical infrastructure. **A2-01M**, ensuring long-term metadata availability, also increased. Minor limitations persist in **A1-05D** (automated machine access) and **A1.2-02D** (authenticated access), suggesting areas for future enhancement.

The Lifestyle Cohort excels in the Interoperability domain. All indicators in this category show either full or nearly full maturity, including those for knowledge representation: **I1-01M/D** and **I1-02M/D**, which focus on the use of standardised and machine-readable representations. The usage of FAIR-compliant vocabularies (**I2-01M/D**) is also well implemented. Importantly, the indicators concerning cross-referencing—**I3-01M**, **I3-01D**, **I3-02M**, **I3-02D**, **I3-03M**, and **I3-04M**—are substantially improved, indicating that the dataset is now embedded in a broader data ecosystem, with proper linkages to other data and metadata resources. This is in contrast to more isolated datasets like the Vaccination Cohort.

The Reusability indicators show a comprehensive level of maturity. **R1-01M** (metadata includes attributes supporting reuse) is well established, and all indicators related to licensing and reuse rights—**R1.1-01M**, **R1.1-02M**, and **R1.1-03M**—are significantly improved, including machine-readable license formats. Both **R1.2-01M** and **R1.2-02M**, which concern provenance

according to community and cross-community standards, show strong maturity. The cohort also demonstrates compliance with community standards (R1.3-01M/D) and the ability to express those standards in machine-readable formats (R1.3-02M/D), suggesting an advanced and reusable data offering.

4.5 Consumer Cohort - My Purchases Cohort

The **My Purchases Cohort** has made commendable progress in implementing FAIR principles, particularly in areas of data discovery, access infrastructure, and interoperability. While some gaps remain in the Reusable category, these are largely due to the pioneering nature of the research field rather than technical shortcomings. Future standardisation efforts may help to close these remaining gaps, enabling full FAIR alignment in the long term. In particular, the **My Purchases Cohort** displays a solid trajectory toward improved FAIR data maturity, with a clearly visible gain in the **Findable**, **Accessible**, and **Interoperable** dimensions. However, progress in the **Reusable** category is more nuanced, reflecting the challenges of working within an emerging research domain where established community standards are not yet available, and where some datasets are maintained and licensed by private operators and organisations such as GS1 <https://www.gs1.dk/>.

The radar plot for Findability reveals a consistent and well-executed improvement across all indicators. The cohort demonstrates high maturity for **F1-01M** and **F1-01D**, which indicates the use of persistent identifiers for both metadata and data. **F1-02M** and **F1-02D**, which focus on globally unique identifiers, also show clear progress. **F2-01M** (rich metadata) and **F4-01M** (harvestable and indexable metadata) are substantially enhanced, contributing to stronger data discoverability. **F3-01M** (metadata includes data identifier) is likewise improved, highlighting cohesive identifier integration across the dataset.

The **Accessible** indicators show broad improvement across all assessed aspects. **A1-01M** (metadata includes access details) achieves top scores, alongside enhancements in **A1-02M** and **A1-02D** for manual accessibility of metadata and data. Improvements in **A1-03M/D** (resolvability), **A1-04M/D** (access via standard protocols), and **A1.1-01M/D** (free protocol access) indicate a well-established and machine-compatible infrastructure. **A1-05D** (automated access for machines) and **A1.2-02D** (authenticated access) also show maturity, while **A2-01M** confirms long-term metadata persistence. This comprehensive progress reflects a well-structured access strategy suitable for both human and programmatic access.

The **Interoperability** dimension of the My Purchases Cohort shows some of the most impressive growth. Indicators like **I1-01M/D** and **I1-02M/D**, which deal with standardised and machine-readable knowledge representations, are significantly improved. **I2-01M/D**, focusing on FAIR-compliant vocabularies, shows similar progress, indicating alignment with widely accepted semantic tools and taxonomies. Additionally, all indicators related to cross-referencing and linking—**I3-01M**, **I3-01D**, **I3-02M/D**, **I3-03M**, and **I3-04M**—have advanced to medium or high maturity. This suggests that the dataset is well-integrated into a broader information ecosystem and capable of being linked with external resources.

The **Reusable** indicators present a mixed picture. While indicators such as **R1-01M** (metadata includes reuse-relevant attributes) and **R1.1-01M** (licensing information) are well addressed,

other areas are constrained by the novelty of the research field. Specifically, indicators related to reuse license standardisation (**R1.1-02M/03M**) and provenance information (**R1.2-01M/02M**) show limited improvement. Most notably, all indicators under **R1.3**—which assess compliance with **community standards** and their **machine-readable expression** (**R1.3-01M, R1.3-01D, R1.3-02M, R1.3-02D**)—remain at the lowest level.

This reflects a **structural limitation** rather than a failure of implementation: **relevant community standards do not yet exist in the emerging research domain of consumer-behaviour-linked purchase cohorts**. As such, these indicators are currently **not applicable** and should be interpreted with this contextual caveat in mind. The cohort may, however, contribute to shaping future standards in this field.

4.6 Wearable Data Collection Study

The **Wearable Cohort** demonstrates a well-balanced and thoughtful approach to implementing FAIR principles within the realistic scope of a feasibility-phase project. Significant improvements in Findability, Accessibility, and Reusability underscore the project's readiness for broader integration. However, **Interoperability remains limited** at this stage, as

expected for a dataset not yet connected to external resources or ontologies. As the project matures and moves toward production-level deployments, integrating these links will be the natural next step to achieving full FAIR compliance. In particular, the **Wearable Cohort** shows a promising trajectory in its FAIR data maturity, especially in the **Findable**, **Accessible**, and **Reusable** dimensions. The radar plots indicate clear improvements in nearly all areas, even though the **Interoperable** dimension remains less developed. This is consistent with the project's current phase: the cohort is part of an **ongoing feasibility study**, meaning the data infrastructure is still being validated, and **cross-referencing to external datasets and metadata has not yet been implemented**.

The Findable indicators show significant and balanced improvements across all categories. The cohort now uses **persistent identifiers** for both metadata (**F1-01M**) and data (**F1-01D**), and also shows marked progress in assigning **globally unique identifiers** (**F1-02M**, **F1-02D**). **F2-01M**, which relates to the richness of metadata for discovery, has been enhanced. The indicators **F3-01M** (metadata includes the identifier for the data) and **F4-01M** (metadata can be harvested/indexed) have also improved, illustrating a clear strategy for making the data findable in both human and machine-readable environments.

In the Accessibility category, the Wearable Cohort demonstrates notable maturity. **A1-01M** (metadata contains information to access the data) scores high, and access mechanisms—both manual (**A1-02M**, **A1-02D**) and via standard protocols (**A1-04M/D**)—are in place. Machine access (**A1-05D**) and authenticated protocols (**A1.2-02D**) show advancement, and **A2-01M** confirms commitment to long-term metadata availability. The presence of free access protocols for both metadata and data (**A1.1-01M/D**) reinforces the accessibility for a wide range of users.

The Interoperability indicators remain the weakest among the four FAIR categories for the Wearable Cohort. While there is gain in **I1-01M/D** and **I1-02M/D** (knowledge representation in standardized and machine-readable formats), and also in **I2-01M/D** (FAIR-compliant vocabularies), **all indicators under I3**—which assess references to other metadata and data (**I3-01M**, **I3-01D**, **I3-02M**, **I3-02D**, **I3-03M**, **I3-04M**)—remain at their baseline level.

This limited progress is **not a shortcoming but a realistic reflection of the project's current stage**. As a **feasibility study**, the **Wearable Cohort is still** establishing basic infrastructure and validating data collection pipelines. It does **not yet include structured links to other datasets or metadata registries**, as such linkages are planned for later phases once data harmonisation and standards are more stable.

The Reusability indicators demonstrate steady and comprehensive progress. **R1-01M** (inclusion of metadata attributes relevant to reuse) is now well addressed. Licensing aspects

(**R1.1-01M**, **R1.1-02M**, **R1.1-03M**) have all been improved, showing the project's intent to enable both legal and technical reuse. Similarly, **R1.2-01M** and **R1.2-02M**, covering provenance standards, show maturity. Compliance with machine-readable community standards (**R1.3-02M/D**) has also been initiated. However, as with other emerging domains, **R1.3-01M/D** may remain partially underdeveloped, as reusable community standards for wearable-derived datasets are still evolving.

5 Summary

The last deliverable of WP7 in the project HEAP, D7.4 Assessment of Interoperability and Data Quality, describes and further explains how the project's interoperability was successfully achieved by continuing data quality and complying with the FAIR principles and GDPR standards. As comprehensively described in this deliverable, the six cohorts have greatly improved the quality and FAIRness of their cohorts during the project duration of HEAP.

Particularly, the Findability and Accessibility dimensions have shown significant progress and have been implemented well within all the six cohorts.

The dimension of Interoperability shows the most diverse evaluation results among all the cohorts. Whereas the interoperability of the Lifestyle Cohort and the Consumer Cohort have improved significantly, in some other cohorts, such as the Wearable Data Collection Study and the HPV Vaccination Cohort, the interoperability aspect is only partially or weakly implemented. This is mainly due to a lack of linked references to other datasets, external metadata records, or metadata registries.

In terms of the Reusable dimension, most of the cohorts have relatively or immensely improved their FAIRness level. Only the HPV Vaccination Cohort shows no improvement but remains steady in this dimension. This is mainly due to the lack of standardisation in expressing data-level community standards and the lack of harmonised exposome standards in the field.

Overall, the evaluation of the Assessment of the six HEAP cohorts is quite satisfactory and can be seen as a rather successful implementation at the end of the 5-year project.

6 References

- FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>
- Dillner, Joakim, Laila Sara Arroyo Mühr, Sara Nordqvist Kleppe, Jiangrong Wang, Helena Andersson, Miriam Elfström, Roxana Merino, and Karin Sundström. 2024. "The Swedish Cervical Screening Cohort." *Scientific Data* 11 (1): 697.
- "HEAP." Catalogue entry, Accessed October 11, 2024.
<https://data-catalogue.molgenisccloud.org/catalogue/ssr-catalogue/EHEN/networks/HEAP>.
- Møller, Frederik T., Thor Grønberg Junker, Kathrine Kold Sørensen, Caroline Eves, Jan Wohlfahrt, Joakim Dillner, Christian Torp-Pedersen, et al. 2023. "Assessing Household Lifestyle Exposures from Consumer Purchases, the My Purchases Cohort." *Scientific Reports* 13 (1): 21601.
- Müller, Heimo, Catarina Lopes-Dias, Petr Holub, Markus Plass, Emilian Jungwirth, Robert Reihls, Paul R. Torke, et al. 2023. "BIBBOX, a FAIR Toolbox and App Store for Life Science Research." *New Biotechnology* 77 (November):12–19.
- Müller, Heimo, Roxana Merino, Stefan Negru, Martin Boeckhout, & Evert-Ben van Veen. (2020). Human Exposome Assessment Platform - Data Management Plan. Public deliverable 7.1. Update Jan 2023 (Final deliverable). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7572272>
- Pimenoff VN, Eriksson T, Vänskä S and Lehtinen M. Finnish Human Papillomavirus Vaccination Cohort. Preprint (biorxiv)
- Pimenoff VN, Öhman H, Kuusiniemi S, Kivelä J, Negru S, Lehtinen M and Surgel HM. Finnish Maternity cohort and related cancer registry linkage. Preprint (biorxiv)
- Sansone, SA., Rocca-Serra, P., Field, D. et al. Toward interoperable bioscience data. *Nat Genet* 44, 121–126 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.1054> (2):121–126. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.1054>.
- Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Annex

FAIR Indicators Used in the HEAP Self-Assessment-Service

These indicators are based on the FAIR Data Maturity Model specifications and guidelines published by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Working Group in 2020.

Indicators for Findable

F1-01M Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier

F1-01D Data is identified by a persistent identifier

F1-02M Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier

F1-02D Data is identified by a globally unique identifier

F2-01M Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery

F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier for the data

F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed

Indicators for Accessible

A1-01M Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data

A1-02M Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)

A1-02D Data can be accessed manually

A1-03M Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record

A1-03D Data identifier resolves to a digital object

A1-04M Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol

A1-04D Data is accessible through standardised protocol

A1-05D Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)

A1.1-01M Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol

A1.1-01D Data is accessible through a free access protocol

A1.2-01D Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation

A2-01M Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available

Indicators for Interoperable

I1-01M Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format

I1-01D Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format

I1-02M Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

I1-02D Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

I2-01M Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

I2-01D Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

I3-01M Metadata includes references to other metadata

I3-01D Data includes references to other data

I3-02M Metadata includes references to other data

I3-02D Data includes qualified references to other data

I3-03M Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata

I3-04M Metadata include qualified references to other data

Indicators for Reusable

R1-01M Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse

R1.1-01M Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused

R1.1-02M Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence

R1.1-03M Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence

R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards

R1.2-02M Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language

R1.3-01M Metadata complies with a community standard

R1.3-01D Data complies with a community standard

R1.3-02M Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard

R1.3-02D Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard